

UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL FLUMINENSE
Instituto de Ciências Humanas e Filosofia
Departamento de Ciência Política
Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciência Política

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**Corporativism in the (re)organization of the Nation-
State:**

Oliveira Vianna and Oliveira Salazar

Supervisor: Professor Claudio de Farias Augusto

Niterói, RJ/Brazil
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DISSERTATION

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in the Postgraduate Program in Political Science at the
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By

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CORPORATIVISM IN THE (RE)ORGANIZATION OF THE NATION-STATE:
OLIVEIRA VIANNA AND OLIVEIRA SALAZAR

DISSERTATION ABSTRACT

The object of our study concerns corporatist proposals of (re) organization in the Nation-State regarding the thought of two contemporary intellectuals: The Brazilian Francisco José de Oliveira Vianna (1883-1951) and the Portuguese António de Oliveira Salazar (1889-1970). Both acted as interpreters of their respective nations, thinking foundational and propositional aspects to what they considered to be crucial back then. These national-corporatist proposals inextricably correlate state restructuring and labor (re) organization and patron at a time of political and economic liberalism crisis. Given the impact of these guidelines in a national level, these intellectuals have engendered decades of both positive and negative realities in their representative countries. In order to accomplish this work, we pay special attention to the analysis of the primary sources relatively unknown in the Social Sciences.

Keywords: Political Experimentalism, Corporatism, Authoritarianism, Democracy, Labor Law.

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